

IMPACT OF JAPANESE MULTIPLICATION TECHNIQUE ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AMONG PRIMARY FIVE PUPILS IN TURETA, SOKOTO STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of Japanese multiplication techniques on academic performance among primary five pupils in Tureta, Sokoto State, Nigeria. It employed quasi-experimental research design entailing pre-test and post-test. A simple random sampling technique through balloting method was used to select two schools out of fifty-six primary schools in Tureta. The two schools selected were assigned as experimental and control groups with a sample of 45 and 70 respectively. The groups were used as intact class. Two objectives and two research questions were raised with their equivalent null hypotheses. Multiplication Performance Test (MPT) was used to collect data. The reliability of the instrument was 0.86 through test retest approach analyzed by using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The data gathered were analyzed by using independent samplet-test at 0.05 level of statistical significance. The findings revealed a significant difference between experimental and control groups in favor of experimental group. But the Japanese Multiplication technique revealed no gender disparity. Among other recommendations include, the professional bodies like MAN, STAN, NMS etc and other educational stake holders should organize workshop and train primary school teachers of this innovative technique.

Keywords: Japanese, Multiplication, Academic Performance

Introduction

Teaching and learning of Mathematics in primary schools is global concerned. Mathematics is considered so important globally that each country makes Mathematics as core subject from the first stage of educational echelon to the highest as a pre-requisite to other discipline. Even with this priority given to Mathematics, still lots of problems arise in the cause of teaching and learning mathematics. The problem may be the curriculum, psychological considerations, philosophical, sociological consideration, historical, administration, evaluation or methodology. The major issue thought to be confronting teaching and learning Mathematics is teaching methodology. Every day and night researchers are sourcing the best method to teach but yet no best method design to teach all concepts in Mathematics. However, many effort has been made to generate a simple and precise method that fit each particular topic. Even with this powerful movement the problems still persist.

The performance of students across all educational edifices is a global concerned. The performance of primary pupils, secondary school students and tertiary institutions students in Mathematics is less than the expected outcomes. These lead the researchers to carry out research across different educational level, different school type, different in students' ability,

different concepts as well as different socioeconomic background. Many researchers believe that if the background or grass root is fixed rigidly with the appropriate method and other teaching resources, the future success may be realized. In primary schools, a lot of materials needed for the success of teaching and learning are either not available at all or are in a sorry state. This poor performance of primary school pupils was attached to teaching methodology employed by the teacher which is the dominant traditional method or chalks and talk method. The importance of basic Mathematical operation (addition, subtraction, division and multiplication) cannot be overemphasized; they are the stepping-stone for greater understanding of other concepts. Even with this significant, still primary pupils find it difficult to multiply two or three-digits - numbers (Wenyuan, 2001). It was gathered by researchers that, primary pupils commit lot of errors in carrying out multiplication by using the traditional method. The errors ranges from missing the place value system, cross multiplying the numbers to inability to add after multiplying out (Wenyuan, 2001). It was gathered by Muhammad and Binji (2017) that, pupils who were taught multiplication by using Japanese technique performed better than those taught by using traditional method. They further revealed no gender disparity when Japanese technique was employed. Their findings is the same as that of Wenyuan (2001) in a similar research conducted in Minnesota. Similarly, Imoka and Isa (2015) in a similar research revealed that pupils who were taught multiplication by using computer game performed better than those taught by using traditional method.

The steps involve in carrying out multiplication by using Japanese technique are demonstrated below with example.

Steps in Japanese Multiplication Technique

The steps are illustrated through the example below

Example: Multiply 12×32

Step1: Draw three parallel lines to represent 12. The first number in the product draw one line and then a little further to the right draw two lines. These lines represent the number 12.

Step 2: Draw five lines to cross the previous three. Three lines at the top and two lines at the bottom. These lines represent the number 32.

Step 3: Group the intersection and make a loop on each group. Starting with the intersection of the last digit of multiplicand and the multiplier

Step 4: So there are 3, 8 and 4 intersection. So by combining the numbers you have 384

Statement of the Problem

Mathematics is a driven tool for science and technology. It's a subject that has both the behavioral, lantern and physical benefit. Mathematics was form due to the incessant needs of human being to explore, utilize, manipulate nature in order to invent and create something that suit his interest. It may be used to explain a hidden and rigorous phenomena. In order to tape the benefit of Mathematics one has to lay a concrete and substantial foundation. This can be done through the use of innovative teaching approach. Unfortunately, in primary schools the dominant teaching approach is lecture method which is characterized as teacher-centered approach. This approach is considered uninteresting to the students towards learning Mathematics (Wenyuan, 2001). The traditional teaching methods in primary schools produce undesirable outcomes in terms of pupils' performance and attitude. The performance of

pupils exposed to traditional method of teaching multiplication is mostly lower than the expected outcomes (Muhammad and Binji, 2017). A lots of measures had being taken to remedy this ugly situation ranging from government effort through seminars, workshops and quality assurance supervision to school effort through the appropriate allocation of subject teacher specialist but little or no improvement was gained. This make it deemed necessary to assess the impact of Japanese multiplication technique on academic performance among primary five pupils in Tureta, Sokoto state, Nigeria in order to give alternative solution to this ugly situation.

Significance of the Study

The study investigated the impact of Japanese multiplication technique on academic performance among primary five pupils in Tureta, Sokoto State, Nigeria. The study investigated the basic concept in Mathematics. The poor performance of pupils in Tureta in the end of term examination in Mathematics is a worry to all and sundry. Hopefully, the finding of this research will benefit pupils by learning a new innovative technique of multiplication. The teachers will also appreciate this multiplication technique and incorporate it in their teaching. Professional bodies and ministries of education can organize workshops and seminars to train teachers of this technique. Curriculum planners can also recommend the use of this technique in teaching multiplication.

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this is to ascertain the impact of Japanese multiplication technique on academic performance among primary five pupils in Tureta, Sokoto State Nigeria. In specific terms, the objectives are:

- i. To investigate the impact of Japanese Multiplication technique on the academic performance of primary five pupils in Tureta.
- ii. To ascertain the impact of Japanese technique on academic performance of primary five pupils before and after the treatment.
- iii. To verify the impact of Japanese multiplication on academic performance of male and female primary five pupils in Tureta.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. Is there difference in the mean performance score of primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique and those taught by using traditional method?
 - ii. Would the performance of primary five pupils taught multiplication vary before and after the treatment
 - iii. What is the difference in the mean performance score between male and female primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique?
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Null Hypotheses

The following hypotheses was generated and tested at 0.05 level of statistical significance”

- i. There’s no significant difference in the mean performance score of primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique and those taught by using traditional method.
- ii. There’s no significant difference in mean performance score of primary fives pupils taught multiplication before and after the treatment.
- iii. There’s no significant difference in the mean performance score of male and female primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique.

Research Design

This study employed quasi experimental design entailing pretest and posttest. This design was employed because it doesn’t require random assignment and classes were used as intact class as school activities cannot be disrupted. Experimental group were exposed to Japanese technique and control group were exposed to traditional method. A pre-test was first administered and a post test was given after the treatment for both groups. The design is illustrated below diagrammatically.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consisted of all primary five pupils in Tureta. There are 56 primary schools with a population of 1370 primary five pupils. The population of the study is presented below based on the educational area.

Table 1: Populations of Primary Five (5) Pupils in Tureta

S/N	Zones	Male	Female	Total
1	Tureta	270	176	446
2	Lambar Tureta	171	73	244
3	Kuruwa	116	65	181
4	Tsamiya	211	63	274
5	Lofa	175	50	225
	Total	943	427	1370

Source: Tureta Local Government Education Authority (TLGEA, 2018)

Sample and Sampling Technique

Simple random sampling technique through balloting method was employed to select two schools out of fifty six (56) primary schools in Tureta. 115 primary five pupils form the sample with 45 and 70 from experimental and control group respectively. The sample is shown below.

Table 2: Sample of the Study

S/N	Name of School	Male	Female	Total	
1	X	30	15	45	EG
2	Y	45	25	70	CG
	Total	75	40	115	

Instrument for Data Collection

Multiplication Performance Test (MPT) was the instrument used to collect data. The instrument consisted of ten (10) essay questions each carries 5 mark making a total of 50 marks. The MPT was administered before and after the treatment. The instrument was validated by five experts in the field of Mathematics education. The result obtained from the pilot study was used to compute the reliability which was found to be 0.86 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC).

Method of Data Analysis

The data gathered was analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the three research questions. In analyzing the hypotheses independent sample t-test was employed to test the first and third null hypotheses at 0.05 level of statistical significance. A paired sample t-test was used in analyzing the second null hypothesis.

Data Presentation

The data collected by using the instrument above are presented below:

Research Question 1

Is there difference in the mean performance score of primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique and those taught by using traditional method?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics Showing the Performances of Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	Mean	Std Dev.
Experimental Group	45	24.76	12.64
Control Group	70	7.20	7.85

From table 3, the mean performance score of pupils exposed to Japanese technique is 24.76 with 12.64 as standard deviation while the mean performance score of pupils exposed to

traditional method is 7.20 with 7.85 as standard deviation. It can vividly see that pupils exposed to Japanese technique performed better than pupils exposed to traditional method.

Research Question 2

What is the impact of Japanese technique on academic performance of primary five pupils before and after the treatment?

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics Showing the Performance of Pupils Exposed to Japanese Technique Before and After the Treatment

Test	N	Mean	Std Dev.
Pre-test	45	5.42	4.25
Post-test	45	24.76	12.64

From table 4, the mean performance score of primary five pupils exposed to Japanese technique at the pretest is 5.42 with 4.25 as standard deviation. While their mean performance score at the posttest is 24.76 with 12.64 as standard deviation. This shows that Japanese technique have great impact on their performance.

Research Question 3

What is the difference in the mean performance between male and female primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique?

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics Showing the Performance of Male and Female Pupils Exposed To Japanese Technique

Gender	N	Mean	Std Dev.
Male	30	25.13	13.23
Female	15	24.00	11.80

Table 5, shows the mean performance score of male pupils as 25.13 and the mean performance score of female pupils as 24.00. The result shows a little difference in their mean performance score.

Null Hypothesis 1

There's no significant difference in the mean performance score of primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique and those taught by using traditional method.

Table 6: Independent Sample t-test for the Performance of Pupils Exposed to Japanese technique and Traditional Method

Groups	N	Mean	Std Dev.	P-value	Decision
Experimental Group	45	24.76	12.64	0.001	H ₀ Rejected
Control Group	70	7.20	7.85		

Decision Criterion: Reject H₀ if $P \leq \alpha(0.05)$

From table 6, the p-value is 0.001 which less than the α -value. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there's significant difference in the mean performance score of primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique and those taught by using traditional method in favor of those exposed to Japanese technique.

Null Hypothesis 2

There's no significant difference in mean performance score of primary fives pupils taught multiplication before and after the treatment.

Table 7: Paired Sample t-test showing the Performance of Pupils Exposed to Japanese Technique Before and After the Treatment

Test	N	Mean	Std Dev.	P-value	Decision
Pre-test	45	5.42	4.25	0.001	H ₀ Rejected
Post-test	45	24.76	12.64		

Table 7, revealed the mean performance of 5.42 and 24.76 for pre-test and post-test respectively. It can be seen that the difference between the mean performance before and after the treatment is 19.34. The p-value is 0.001 which is less than α (0.05). Therefore, we reject H₀ and conclude that there's significant difference in mean performance of primary five pupils taught multiplication before and after the treatment of Japanese technique.

Null Hypothesis 3

There's no significant difference in the mean performance score of male and female primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique.

Table 8: Independent Sample t-test showing the Performance of Male and Female Pupils Exposed To Japanese Technique

Gender	N	Mean	Std Dev.	P-value	Decision
Male	30	25.13	13.23	0.396	H ₀ Retained
Female	15	24.00	11.80		

From the table above, the p-value is 0.396 which is greater than α -value (0.05). Therefore, we failed to reject H₀ and conclude that there's no significant difference in the mean performance of male and female primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique. Hence, the technique is gender friendly.

Discussion of the Result

The result revealed that, there's significant difference in the mean performance of primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique and those taught by using traditional method in favor of those taught with the earlier technique. It shows the impact of Japanese technique on pupils' academic performance. The finding also agreed with that of Wenyan (2001) and Muhammad and Binji (2017). Similarly, the second hypothesis

revealed a significant difference in mean performance of primary five pupils taught multiplication before and after the treatment of Japanese technique. A great difference exists between the two tests, the impact of Japanese technique is vividly shown with the large difference in their mean performance. The third hypothesis revealed no gender difference in the mean performance of primary five pupils taught multiplication by using Japanese technique. Japanese technique is gender friendly. It also agreed with findings of Muhammad and Binji (2017).

Conclusion

The findings of this research revealed the impact of Japanese technique on primary five pupils' academic performance. It probed a significant impact better than the conventional method. It further revealed a great improvement on the performance of primary five pupils after the treatment being given. The technique can be used to bridge gender disparity as the finding revealed no significant difference among the genders.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this research the following recommendations were made:

1. The federal ministry of basic and secondary education, state universal basic education and local government education authority should organize workshops and train primary school teacher about this method of multiplication.
2. The professional bodies like Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN) and Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) should organize workshops to be captured in their annual conference about this method.
3. The researchers should also investigate on retention and attitude with regard to this Japanese multiplication strategy.

References

- Clement, D. H. (2002). *Rethinking Concrete Manipulative. Teaching Children Mathematics* 2 (5): 270-279. Retrieved from www.encyclopedia.com/doc/IGI-1723767.html on 1st July, 2016.
- Douglas, O. & Olsen, N. (2008). The Effects of the Multiple Intelligence Teaching Strategy On Academic Achievement Of Eight Grade Math Students. *Journal of Instructional Psychology*, 35 (2): 182-187
- Gugliotta, K.F. (2010). *Gender Difference In Attitude Towards Mathematics And Science Among Elementary Students: An Exploration of The Role of Teachers*. University of Tennessee Honors Thesis Projects. Retrieved from <http://www.trace.tennessee.edu/utkchanhonoproj/1386> on 28th August, 2016
- Inekwe, I. O. (2002). Sensitising Students Learning Of Mathematics Through Affective Means: A Focus On The Universal Basic Education. *Nigeria Educational Forum. A Journal of Institute of Education, ABU Zaria*, 16 (7): 76-81.
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- Muhammad, N. H. & Binji, B. U. (2016). Effect Of Gelosia Method Of Multiplication On Primary Five Pupils' Mathematics Performance In Sokoto South Local Government (A Case Study of Dallatu Model Primary School). *International Journal of Contemporary Education and Management (IJCEM)*. **11** (2): 35-44. ISBN 3609-7086
- Ministry of Education (1958). *Teaching Mathematics in Secondary Schools*, London press limited.
- Odili, G. A. (2006). *Mathematics In Nigeria Secondary School,: A Teacher's Perspective* published by REX Charles and Patrick limited in Association with Anachuna Educational Books – Port Harcourt
- Wenyuan, G. U. (2001). *The Lattice Method Use in Teaching Multiplication with Whole Numbers and Decimals to Students With Learning Disabilities*. Department of special education, Winona State University Minnesota.
- Yagar, R. (2001). The Constructivist Learning Model: Towards Real Reform in Science Education. *Rt5 The Science teacher*, **58** (6) 52-57.